

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B316
Date: 15 August 2007
Take Off 07:53:32Z
Landing: 09:09:42Z
Flight Time 1h16m10s

Campaign: COPS

Operating Area: Cranfield to Baden Baden Transit

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM 1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Stephen Mobbs	NCAS
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Stuart Heath	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	Mission Scientist 2	Justin Peter	University of Leeds
9	Observer	Victoria Smith	University of Leeds
10	Engineering Supervisor 1	John Kitchen	Avalon Aero
11	Engineering Supervisor 2	Andrew Boardman	Avalon Aero
12	Operations Manager	Peter Chappell	Directflight
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Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B316
 Date: 15 August 2007
 Project: COPS
 Location: Cranfield to Baden Baden

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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073623		Start-Up	0.87 kft	128	52'04.36N ,0'37.48W
075332		T/O	1.4 kft	213	Cranfield
080214		Video	13.2 kft	104	Start FFC & DFC
090942		Land	0.50 kft	133	Baden Baden
091457		Shutdown	0.51 kft	161	48'46.91N, 8'05.35E

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B316 Track 15-AUG-07

PROJECT BRIEF: COPS - Convective and Orographically-induced Precipitation Study.

Scientific Aims: The goals of UK-COPS are to determine the mechanisms for transport of aerosols into the convective clouds that form over the Black Forest mountains, to determine the properties of the aerosols and to understand the formation and growth of ice and precipitation in these clouds. We wish to examine:

- the structure of the thermally driven, turbulent boundary-layer flows below cloud base
- the properties of the representative aerosol particles in the clear air that are transported into the convective clouds
- the concentration and size of cloud droplets just above cloud base
- the formation of the first ice due to primary nucleation on ice nuclei (IN)
- the development of ice via secondary processes such as the Hallett-Mossop process, in which new ice particles are generated during the riming growth of ice particles
- other secondary ice production processes, such as evaporative break-up;
- the production of supercooled raindrops and their role in the glaciation process
- the dependence of these processes on the dynamics of the cloud
- the production of precipitation

There will be one flight per day to observe the airflow and aerosol properties entering the convective clouds and most importantly, the properties of the clouds themselves. Measurements will be made in cumulus clouds when their tops are about 0°C through to when the tops have grown to about -20°C.

Weather conditions:

Developing showers over the Black Forest mountains, Germany, within Box A and probably B.

Safety: Regions that paint RED on the aircraft weather radar should be avoided. No flight into clouds known to be producing lightning.

Key instruments and their operation:

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer
- GPS, INU, turbulence probe. When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud Physics/Aerosol

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, CDP, CIP, SID-1 and SID-2. Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits, appearance of large drops ($d > 100 \mu\text{m}$) in 2D imagery when above freezing level.
- CCN measurements should be made by filling the alleviator whilst in clear air runs.
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where straight/level and in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Managers log.
- TWC - profile ascents/descents should avoid cloud if possible
- CVI - below cloud base, normal operation is in aerosol mode; above cloud base, normal operation is in CVI mode

Sortie Brief: COPS – Convective and Orographically-induced Precipitation Study
Flight Number: B316
Date: 15 August 2007
Mission Scientists:
TO Time: local

Sortie Aims: To measure properties of aerosols and airflow in the clear air and the development of convective clouds.

Sortie Location: Clear air above Murg Valley and in convective clouds over Black Forest mountains. Leg over supersites.

Sortie Summary:

1. Observe the boundary layer structure over one of the principal valleys penetrating the Black Forest mountain region.
2. Characterise properties of aerosols in clear air at low levels over the Black Forest, and the airflow over the Black Forest.
3. Penetrate cumulus clouds preferably near the top of the cloud in the updraught. All cloud penetrations should be with *wings level*. Two principal options are:
 - A stationary cloud or system of clouds;
 - B several cumulus clouds either in area (low wind) or passing through the area;
4. Characterise properties of aerosols in detrainment layers around cloud.
5. Overfly supersites M, H and R.

Sortie Detail:

1. Out-of-Cloud: All changes in altitude at standard rates (1000 ft/min).

Proceed to point C. Straight and level legs over the Murg Valley along track C-B and returning along track B-C (as flight B312, 26 July). Repeat at 5.0, 6.0 and 7.5 kft above mean sea level.

2. Cloud work:

Note an important feature is to ascend with tops. This requires a non-standard ascent as fast as possible.

Option A: Isolated developing clouds – ascend with the clouds near their top. All penetrations at constant altitude.

A.1 Proceed to about 0°C or top of cloud.

A.2 Adjust altitude to about 1000 ft below cloud top and penetrate cloud. The penetration should be made at a constant azimuth and altitude if possible. It is important to penetrate the growing turret in the updraught region. A few seconds after clearing cloud, turn and ascend for return to same region of cloud as quickly as possible using procedure turn.

A.3 Repeat A.2, ascending with the top (if appropriate) at the end of each penetration out of cloud, until FL200 or FL240, or cloud becomes too developed.

A.4 Repeat A.1 - A.3 for a new developing cumulus, go to **Option B**, or exit box.

Option B: Many developing cumulus clouds – sample clouds at constant altitude.

B.1 Proceed to 0°C

B.2 Commence 10 min runs (turning where appropriate) in along shear direction. Adjust track to randomly sample the updraught regions of growing turrets.

B.3 Ascend to -5°C (i.e. approximately 3500 ft) and repeat above for 10 min.

B.4 Repeat for -10°C , -15°C and -20°C if possible.

3. Detrainment layers

Proceed to level where cloud is being detrained from cloud and either make penetrations or circle around the cloud.

4. Leg over supersites Murg Valley (M), Hornisgrinde (H) and Achern (R) at about 5500 ft if in clear air. (15 min). Please make SATCOM phone call to Ops Centre 15 mins before overpass of Supersites: 07229 66 2550, or 2551.

EDSB -> EDDS - Overview

NavData Cycle 2007-7 Expires: Thursday, 02 August 2007.
Scale: 1:426851 (1 inch = 5.85 naut mi). Printed on 18 Jul 2007

JEPPESEN
FliteStar 9.2.0.2

Flight:

B316

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevzorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 20/08/2007
17:30:19

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

20/08/2007 17:12:36

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B312

Date: 26/07/2007

Instruments

1. FFC – not on video pre-flight. Probably not reconnected after NEON. Reconfigured at Titler then okay.
2. TWC – status light came on at FL270, -28C outside, Status word 4091, Para 72 TSAM out of limits (640) , TSAM reading 637 DRS units. Also, Para 75 EVAP 1 below limit (2110), reading 2089 DRSU.
3. Satcom C – Position reports being Queued but not sent. Reset CB, stopped and resubmitted messages then okay. Also, occasional messages “Satcom hardware status unavailable” at Menu option 5 – Show hardware status.
- 4.

Aircraft

- 1.

Satcom-H Calls

Hornisgrinde

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B316:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Mission Scientist's log	Transit flight so possibly no de-brief. Stephen Mobbs may still create one.
De-brief	Transit flight so possibly no de-brief. Stephen Mobbs may still create one.
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	02 Oct 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1	15 Jan 2008	Doug Anderson	Updated video tape holder information
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

- 1 x Forward Facing Camera
- 1 x Downward Facing Camera

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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